

PHOTODYNAMIC THERAPY ON CERVICAL CANCER

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ABSTRACT:

This review aims to provide an overview of the effectiveness of the photodynamic therapy on cervical cancer caused by human papilloma virus based on the research results done among more than 800 women. As there is an increase in the number of cervical cancer incidence among the young and pregnant females makes this study on photodynamic therapy more important as this therapy guarantees 99.9% of cure without destroying the normal anatomy and histology of the cervix. While other techniques like trachelectomy, cryotherapy and laser therapies has high recurrence rates and it causes damage to the parts of the cervix.

KEYWORDS: Photodynamic therapy, human papilloma virus, cervical cancer, intraepithelial neoplasia, complete response to HPV.

INTRODUCTION:

Cervical cancer becomes a major threat as the third most prevalent malignancy among the women population with an increasing incidence between the age group of 20 to 49 years[1]. It is an intraepithelial neoplasia of cervix caused by Human Papilloma Virus [HPV], which is transmitted by sexual contact. According to studies, there are more than 180 strains of HPV have been discovered. Still the strain 16 and 18 are the most common types imposing a great risk for developing cervical cancer[2], because other strains of HPV incidence can be neutralized by our own immune system. The main focus of using photodynamic therapy in cervical lesion is to avoid the complications like treatment related infertility, early menopause, kidney failure and fistula formation which leads to poor quality of life. This new technique of PDT became a valuable and promising treatment [3] for cervical cancer which works on the principle of applying the photosensitizer over

the neoplastic cells and by using a particular wavelength beam of light will be focused over the particular part leading to the release of oxygen reactive species causing the destruction of particular abnormal neoplastic cells leaving the normal cells .

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

We have made a literature review based on the research results done by researchers across the globe to prove the efficacy of the use of photodynamic therapy over the cervical lesions without causing complications and decreasing the incidence of remission.

PDT MECHANISM OF ACTION IN CERVICAL CANCER:

The Photodynamic therapy was first used by Kennedy in 1990 over HPV lesions[4]. Later the research by the Mexican scientists lead by Eva Ramon Gallegos shows it can be used for cervical cancer by clearing almost every neoplastic cell in CIN-1[low – grade variety of neoplasia][5]. It works on the mechanism of applying photosensitizer over the neoplastic lesions locally and a particular wavelength beam of light will be focused to form oxygen reactive species to kill the cell by itself without causing damage to the nearby cells as the half- life of photosensitizer will be more in the neoplastic cells than the normal cells. Most commonly used photosensitizer is Hexyl- Amino Levulinic Acid [6]

[ALA] at concentrations of 10-20% applied topically over the cervix .Then it penetrates every local cell and roughly with an incubation period of four to eight hours it gets converted into a light sensitive compound called protoporphyrin-IX which is maximally get accumulated in the neoplastic cells as this compound has less half-life in the normal cells. After that the photosensitized lesion was irradiated with a tungsten lamp using a specific wavelength of 400-700 nm for 15 to 20 minutes causing the neoplastic cells to form the oxygen reactive species like super oxides causing its own death. Typically, there will be 1 to 6 sessions of therapy with an interval of 1-2 weeks[4]. It has only simple side effects like burning

sensation and a milder pain by maintaining the cervical structure unlike other treatment techniques.

CONCLUSION:

Photodynamic therapy is an effective treatment method over other traditional methods for cervical cancer without causing treatment related complications with a higher success rate and a lower. recurrence rate.

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